

MEASURES TAKEN TO AVOID THE POLLUTION OF NATURAL AND ARTIFICIAL ATMOSPHERE

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Annotation: *This article discusses the specific conditions of environmental issues related to the circulation of the atmosphere through natural and artificial processes, current ecological problems, and several measures taken to mitigate artificial pollution.*

Key terms: *Atmosphere, Earth's surface, permissible levels, chemical substances, harmful elements, organisms, Sanitary Norms and Rules (SanPIN).*

Introduction. Scientific and technological advancement, although evolving through various complex and sophisticated processes, still faces unresolved challenges within the framework of the interrelation between Society-Earth-Human-Community.

One such critical issue is the escalating risks posed by environmental hazards. Upon generalizing and analyzing the incidents occurring in various corners of our planet over time, it becomes evident that anthropogenic, natural, and ecological crises are increasing annually, posing a threat to vast territories.

First President I. Karimov emphasized: Ecology is one of the acute social issues of modern times, the resolution of which is crucial for the benefit of all nations. The current and future civilization largely depends on the resolution of these issues."

The high responsibility of our society members - the duty to preserve natural resources and responsibly utilize them for sustainable benefits, as well as the task of environmental protection outlined in the State Basic Law, which ensures a unified state policy in combating climate change, epidemics, pandemics, and mitigating their consequences.

Particularly, the Constitution grants the right to access reliable information about the state of the environment in Article 49, and in Article 68, it emphasizes the national importance of Earth, subsoil resources, water, flora and fauna, and other natural resources, stressing the necessity for their rational use and state protection.

Research Objective. The atmosphere, as the air crust of the Earth, is one of the primary sources ensuring the existence of life in the biosphere. It shields all living organisms from harmful cosmic rays and regulates the temperature on the planet's surface. Increased air pollution, especially from particulate matter, leads to a sharp increase in the population's illness rate.

Atmospheric pollution is particularly harmful to humans. Pollutants in the air are mainly absorbed through the respiratory system. Particles with a radius of 0.01-0.1 micrometers make up 50% of all pollutants suspended in the air.

Workers exposed to asbestos are at a higher risk of developing cancer. Beryllium can harm the respiratory tract, skin, and eyes. Diesel fumes can lead to damage to the nervous and respiratory systems.

Air pollution is the greatest ecological threat to public health worldwide, causing an estimated 7 million premature deaths annually. The pollution of the atmosphere and climate change are closely related, as all major pollutants affect the climate and the majority of them distribute general sources with greenhouse gases. The UNEP alert on pollution movement underscores the global state of air pollution, its primary sources, its impact on human health, and encourages national efforts to address this crucial issue.

The practical results of the research are as follows. In the 2023 World Air Quality Report, it was observed that the four most polluted countries in the world are located in the Central and South Asian region, including Bangladesh, India, Tajikistan, and Pakistan. Additionally, within this region, some of the most polluted cities globally include Delhi in India, Lahore in Pakistan, and Tashkent in Uzbekistan. Each city's annual average PM2.5 concentration distribution demonstrates that the concentration of pollutants in urban areas is more than ten times higher than the WHO annual average guideline value.

The main factors contributing to the pollution of our region's atmosphere are industrial emissions, ongoing construction activities, agriculture through the cultivation of cotton and other crops, and deforestation. The dust particles carried by winds from the deserts in our region get trapped in the Himalayan mountain range, causing changes in temperature. This leads to the detection of dust storms in our country through strong winds, contributing to the world's worst air pollution.

As industrialization continues to grow worldwide, harmful gases are emitted into the atmosphere, causing significant damage to agricultural crops. According to long-

term monitoring results, the amount of ecological harmful chemical compounds emitted into the atmosphere, the composition of their particulates, and the elements of ash from combustion products double every 12-14 years, making atmospheric pollution one of the global issues. Atmospheric pollution refers to changes in its composition and characteristics, negatively affecting human health, animals, plants, and ecosystems. Currently, 75% of atmospheric pollution is attributed to natural sources, while 25% is attributed to anthropogenic sources.

The solution to the problem lies in minimizing the substances that harm the atmosphere as much as possible. As we gradually destroy the biosphere and atmosphere, we ultimately harm our own health.

In conclusion, the results of these conducted experimental investigations indicate that the pollution of our atmosphere by major industrial enterprises emitting large amounts of highly dispersed particles and gases, the continued growth of construction, the increase in global temperatures with dramatic consequences such as Arctic melting, a significant increase in the water level of the world's oceans, increased soil erosion, and ultimately, the various levels of atmospheric pollution and its direct exposure to harmful gases.

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